

IMPLEMENTING PROJECT PSIS (PROXIMITY CONTROL, SIGNAL INTERFERENCE, IGNORING, AND STUDENT ARRANGEMENT) TO MINIMIZE DISRUPTIVE BEHAVIORS OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS: AN ACTION RESEARCH

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 8

Pages: 990-1001

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2207

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13315685

Manuscript Accepted: 06-27-2024

Implementing Project PSIS (Proximity Control, Signal Interference, Ignoring, and Student Arrangement) To Minimize Disruptive Behaviors of Grade 7 Students: An Action Research

Jonelson C. Escandallo,* Novie May C. Manliguez, Kheyzza M. Panizales, Venus M. Pupa, Alaiza Mae C. Villamor, Deveyvon L. Espinosa, Conie B. Cerna, Kristy Jane R. Muegna, Regine L. Generalao

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the disruptive behaviors exhibited by Grade 7 students at Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School, exploring the reasons behind these behaviors, the experiences they faced, how they coped with them, and their perspectives on their situations. Employing a descriptive quantitative approach using pretest and posttest methods, the study involved Grade 7 students at the school. Through in-depth interviews, observations, and survey questionnaires, it was found that the participants had significant experiences and challenges, including struggling with various disruptive behaviors among their classmates. The findings also revealed that Grade 7 students managed these challenges by ignoring their classmates and utilizing the PROJECT PSIS (Proximity control, Signal interference, Ignoring, and Student arrangement) strategy, as well as maintaining dedication and self-discipline. Ultimately, the study emphasized the need for support from parents, teachers, and the entire school community to mitigate these behaviors.

Keywords: *disruptive behavior, students, teachers, parents, PSIS*

Introduction

The disruptive behavior of the students relates to the various actions which can possibly hinder the teaching and learning process of both learners and teachers. It can be physical and verbal aggression, moving in class, fails to follow classroom regulations, as well as the improper gestures. With this, classroom management served as the foundation to establish an effective and conducive learning environment that can deal and assist the students who have disruptive behavior inside the classroom (Caldarella et al., 2021).

In international context specifically in Bhutan, disruptive behavior of the Bhutanese students was evident because the mentioned country faced a major challenge every time the English language was taught by the teachers. As a result, it had been alleged that the students had a poor level of involvement which was the cause of their misbehavior in the classroom. In addition to this, it had an impact on their learning outcomes and performance as learners (Wangdi, 2022).

Moreover, in Dasmariñas City, Philippines, disruptive behavior in the secondary schools has become a great problem. Teachers have complaints against behavioral problems of the students since it can affect the whole class. Also, the classrooms where disruptive behavior occurs frequently gets less academic engaged time, and the students in distracted classrooms stand in low category in achievement tests. Further, it attempts to control the disruptive behaviors and its considerable time of the teachers at the expense of academic instructions in the class. So, school discipline issues such as disruptive behavior and violence also have an increased effect on teacher stress and burnout (Gabanán, 2023).

In the Division of Davao del Norte, particularly in Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School it was observed that the presence of disruptive behavior in two class sections of grade 7 which are Rose and Carnation affects the process of transmitting the teaching and learning process. If the students caught the attention of the whole class during class hours with their disruptive behavior it can decrease the sense of safety among students, which may result in increased bullying. Additionally, the student who is disrupting the learning of the peer can also face problems and can feel isolated from their classmates, which can lead to emotional distress and loneliness.

The urgency and social relevance of disruptive behaviors among grade 7 students are significant concerns in educational settings. When left unaddressed, disruptive behaviors can hinder open discussions, diminish engagement, and disrupt the sense of community that fosters intellectual growth, ultimately affecting the overall learning environment and academic performance of students. Disruptive behaviors can lead to impaired learning, poor academic performance, and teacher burnout and turnover. Understanding the factors contributing to disruptive behavior, such as social skills deficits, peer influence, and classroom environment, is crucial for addressing these issues effectively. Educators and school personnel can implement strategies that promote a positive learning environment, enhance social skills development, and provide teachers with resources and training to effectively manage disruptive behavior.

The research gap in the disruptive behaviors of grade 7 students at Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School lies in the need for culturally relevant and up-to-date descriptions of these behaviors in the school's specific context. Existing scales and studies may not fully capture the diverse and evolving forms of misbehavior exhibited by students in this setting. For instance, while some studies have identified common behaviors such as verbal abuse, forgetfulness, and nonattentiveness, others have reported behaviors like daydreaming, sleeping, and bullying that may not be fully represented in existing scales. Moreover, the cultural and social dynamics

of the school, may require unique and context-specific strategies to effectively address and manage disruptive behavior. Therefore, there is a need for descriptive quantitative research to uncover the specific and contemporary problem behaviors exhibited by grade 7 students at Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School and to develop culturally relevant interventions to address these issues effectively.

Research Questions

The study focuses on exploring and understanding the implementation of classroom management strategies that can address the disruptive behavior of grade 7 students. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following:

1. What is the level of disruptive behaviors among Grade 7 students before the utilization of PSIS intervention?
2. What is the level of disruptive behaviors among Grade 7 students after the utilization of PSIS intervention?
3. What insights can you share to the school administrators, teachers, and stakeholders with regards to action intervention taken?

Literature Review

The researchers proposed the implementation of PROJECT PSIS (Proximity Control, Signal Interference, Ignoring, and Student Arrangement) as a comprehensive and effective classroom management strategy aimed at minimizing disruptive behaviors. By utilizing techniques such as adjusting teacher proximity, managing signal interference, strategically ignoring misbehavior and optimizing student seating arrangements, this approach directly addresses common classroom issues. Furthermore, PROJECT PSIS enhances the quality of teacher-student interactions, creating a more conducive learning environment. It also promotes a culture of respect and discipline during class discussions, ensuring that all students can engage more productively and attentively.

The purpose of PROJECT PSIS (Proximity Control, Signal Interference, Ignoring, and Student Arrangement) is to provide a structured and targeted classroom management approach for Grade 7 students who require additional support to engage and learn effectively. This comprehensive strategy involves several key components designed to address specific classroom issues and enhance teacher-student interactions.

The Proximity control is a classroom management strategy that involves teachers strategically positioning themselves near students who are prone to distractions or disruptive behavior. By being physically close to these students, teachers can maintain focus and deter negative behaviors like talking or laughing with their seatmates without having to explicitly call them out in front of their peers. This approach helps to create a sense of accountability among students, encouraging them to stay on task and avoid misbehavior. The proximity of the teacher serves as a subtle reminder to the student that they are being monitored and that their behavior is being observed. This can be particularly effective for students who are easily distracted or prone to misbehavior, as it helps them stay focused on the lesson and avoid engaging in off-task behaviors. By moving closer to the student, the teacher can also provide a sense of support and guidance, helping the student to refocus and regain control over their behavior.

Additionally, Signal Interference is a classroom management strategy that involves teachers using subtle cues or signals to interrupt potential disruptions like moving the student's armchair and frequently going outside before they escalate, redirecting student attention back to the lesson. This technique is designed to prevent misbehavior from escalating into more significant disruptions, thereby maintaining a positive and productive learning environment. Signal interference is particularly effective in preventing misbehavior from escalating because it addresses the issue early on. By interrupting the behavior before it becomes more significant, the teacher can prevent the disruption from spreading and causing further distractions. This approach also helps to maintain a sense of control and order in the classroom, as students learn to recognize and respond to the teacher's cues.

In addition, Ignoring is a classroom management strategy that involves temporarily ignoring misbehavior like the students wants an attention that do not significantly disrupt the class. This approach is designed to prevent these actions from drawing undue attention and escalating into more significant disruptions. By ignoring these misbehaviors, teachers can maintain a positive classroom atmosphere by not giving undue attention to these behaviors. Ignoring misbehavior is particularly effective in managing classroom behavior because it helps to reduce the frequency and intensity of these behaviors over time. When teachers ignore these behaviors, they are essentially withholding the attention that these behaviors previously received. This can be a powerful way to teach students that certain behaviors are not worthy of attention and that they need to find alternative ways to express themselves.

Furthermore, Student Arrangement involves carefully designing seating arrangements that optimize student interactions and minimize conflicts. This component of PROJECT PSIS aims to group students in ways that promote positive behavior and collaboration, creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment. The key to effective Student Arrangement lies in the teacher's ability to analyze the dynamics of the classroom and make informed decisions about seating placements. This may involve separating students who tend to distract each other, placing students who need more support closer to the teacher, or grouping students with complementary strengths and learning styles together.

By integrating these components, PROJECT PSIS aims to create a learning environment where all students, particularly those in Grade 7, can thrive. It addresses the specific needs of this age group, which often experiences significant developmental and behavioral changes, ensuring that classroom management strategies are both effective and supportive. This approach not only mitigates disruptive

behaviors but also fosters a respectful and disciplined atmosphere conducive to learning and engagement.

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized a quantitative approach with a pre-experimental, descriptive one-group pretest-posttest design. As explained by Thyer (2012), it describes one-group pretest-posttest design as involving a single group of participants observed at two points in time: before (pretest) and after (posttest) an intervention. Efficacy studies, which investigate the effects of specific treatments or interventions, use this design to determine if the treatment yields positive outcomes. It is an effective method for identifying any changes in indicators that occur as a result of the intervention.

This method is necessary in pursuing this action research wherein the aim is to assess how effective a strategy is by selecting and choosing the respondents to be tested using pre-test and post-test conducted by the researchers. The researchers will use the intervention namely "Proximity control, signal interference, ignoring, student arrangement (PSIS)" which aims to address the needs of disruptive behaviors among Grade 7 students. There will be a prior survey and after the implementation of intervention, a final survey will be conducted. The study is quantitative as it includes the numerical data of the identified respondents and the mean obtained from the data, which makes it suited for quantitative study.

Participants

This study was conducted at Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National School, a secondary public school situated in Purok 3, Capungagan, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. In the selection of the participants, the head of the English department in Grade 7 identified the students that are qualified for the study. Cohen (2007) advised that a quantitative study to be conducted with heterogeneous group would comprise at least 14 participants. In this study the researchers will have thirty-three (89) Grade 7 students, with the help of the Head of English department and the teachers inside the school, students will be as respondents in the study. The participants are mainly from Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School. Moreover, this study employed purposive sampling, a type of non-probability sampling, involves the deliberate selection of specific individuals based on their relevance to the research. This method is particularly useful when the researcher has specific knowledge about the population and can select a sample that is most representative of the population (Curtis, 2011).

Table 1. *Respondents*

<i>Grade</i>	<i>Number of Students</i>
Carnation	46
Rose	43
Total	89

Instruments

The researchers in this study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire, meticulously designed based on the indicators outlined in Wangdi and Namgyel's (2022) work, "Classroom to Reduce Student Disruptive Behavior." This questionnaire was adopted because it directly pertains to the specific focus of the study which is the disruptive behavior among students. By aligning the questionnaire with established indicators from a relevant and recent study, the researchers ensured that the instrument was both valid and reliable for measuring the targeted behaviors. This alignment also facilitated a comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to and mitigating disruptive behaviors in classroom settings. The tailored nature of the questionnaire allowed for precise data collection on the prevalence, types, and contexts of such behaviors, thereby providing robust insights that could inform effective intervention strategies and educational policies.

Moreover, the researchers provided five-point Likert scale to measure and identify the status of reading comprehension of the students involved in the study. Upon utilization, the respondents will just put a check (✓) mark on the box appropriate on their level. The scale ranges from very high to very low, consisting range of means from 5.0 as the highest and 1.0 as the lowest. The following table will show the range of means, description and the corresponding interpretation of the scale provided.

Likert Scale on Level of Reading Comprehension

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptions</i>	<i>Interpretations</i>
4.30 – 5.00	Very High	The measure described in the disruptive behaviors among Grade 7 students is always manifested.
3.50 – 4.20	High	The measure described in the disruptive behaviors among Grade 7 students is oftentimes manifested.
2.70 – 3.40	Moderate	The measure described in the disruptive behaviors among Grade 7 students is sometimes manifested.
1.90 – 2.60	Low	The measure described in the disruptive behaviors among Grade 7 students is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	The measure described in the disruptive behaviors among Grade 7 students is rarely manifested.

Data Procedure

The methods that the researchers will be using in data collection are the 14 participants who undergone In-Depth Interview (IDI) and

Focus Group Discussion (FGD) interviews to formulate themes. IDI's allow participants to share experiences openly in a safe environment without hesitation and allows researchers to pursue new themes that emerge during the interview. FDG's are chosen to explore diverse views on a particular phenomenon through group discussion and interaction of prominent issues. According to Boyce and Neale (2006) in this method, the dialogue does not involve asking a set of predetermined question as the case of the quantitative surveys.

The researchers will record the participants' responses. A researchers must grasp the nature of the research and the rationale for doing the study in order to introduce and obtain permission from respondents to perform the study and include them in the quest, to conduct focus group discussions. The researchers ensure that all relevant measures for data collection are appropriately planned.

As the research starts off, the researchers will cultivate favorable relationships with the participants and request permission to undertake the study. The flow of the discussion and the letter of communication will provide information for the participants. Furthermore, before the formal discussion, participants will be orientated and given the opportunity to read the research questions of this endeavor. In addition, the replies of participants will be recorded, and everyone will receive a copy of the discussion guide. The researchers will next ensure that the procedure is done in a way that is sensitive to people. According to Creswell (2008), a study entails a wide range of data collecting as the researchers strives to construct an in-depth perspective on the study.

Therefore, the process of collecting data is to compare the disruptive behavior before the classroom management has been implemented. The researchers will provide her own research plan to be given to the participants and will be interviewed on the status of student disruptive behavior after classroom management to lessen the disruptive behavior has been implemented.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researchers utilized the qualitative data analysis consists of coding and categorizing patterns or themes found in the data (Denzin & Lincoln, 2003). Through the interview guide questions, the researchers ask open-ended inquiries. During the interview, all audio recordings are transcribed. The data are then coded and thematically examined in response to the study questions.

In the process of qualitative analysis, researchers utilized a method known as coding to delve into the intricacies of their data. This involves the identification of key concepts within the responses provided by participants. By meticulously examining the responses, the researchers discern relationships between different answers and establishes connections among them. Coding serves as the analytical bridge, enabling the researchers to assign words or concise phrases that encapsulate the essence of the participants' responses. This systematic approach not only facilitates the organization of data but also unveils patterns and themes, allowing for a nuanced and comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under investigation.

Subsequent to the coding phase, the researchers actively engage in the application of thematic analysis, a methodical approach aimed at identifying, analyzing, organizing, describing, and reporting prevalent themes within the dataset, as delineated by Braun and Clarke (2006). The extracted data undergo a meticulous categorization process, wherein the researchers systematically cluster them into discernible themes. Within this intricate process, emphasis is placed on generating meaning from the amalgamation of central ideas that emerge from the coded responses. The researchers, in the role of an interpreter, then delves into the nuanced interpretation of these themes, thereby imbuing them with depth and significance. Finally, the outcomes of this analytical journey are meticulously presented, ensuring a comprehensive and insightful representation of the data.

On the other hand, the study utilized quantitative research because it allowed for the systematic measurement and analysis of numerical data to describe, explain, predict, or control variables and phenomena of interest. This analysis was chosen to provide a precise and objective understanding of the topic, which is particularly important when generalizability and external validity are crucial. The quantitative method also enabled the researchers to use statistical techniques to analyze the data, ensuring that the results were consistent and replicable. Additionally, the use of quantitative methods allowed for the collection of data from a large sample size, which is essential for ensuring that the findings are representative of the broader population.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results, analysis, and interpretation of the findings of the study. The data are presented in both tabular and textual forms. The findings relate to the research questions that guided the study.

Level of Disruptive Behaviors Among Grade 7 Students Before and After the Utilization of PSIS Intervention in Terms of Talking Inside the Classroom

The Table 1.1 presents the pre-test data obtained from this indicator among Grade 7 students revealed that their disruptive behaviors in terms of talking inside the classroom has been manifested as High, accumulating 4.05 mean score from a range of 3.50-4.20 as stated in the scale.

Table 1.1. *Pre-Test Data Obtained from this Indicator Among Grade 7 Students*

<i>Talking Inside the Classroom</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
constantly chatting with seatmate despite repeated warnings.	3.93	High

engaging in loud conversations, disrupting the teacher's instructions.	4.12	High
ignoring the teacher's requests to remain quiet during lectures.	3.68	High
initiating off-topic discussions, derailing the focus of the class.	4.24	Very High
persistently whispering or passing notes, causing distractions to fellow students.	4.28	Very High
Overall Mean	4.05	High

Moreover, it showcases the overall mean of disruptive behaviors related to talking inside the classroom before the PSIS intervention among grade 7 students is 4.05, which is categorized as "High". Notably, the behavior of item 5 "persistently whispering or passing notes, causing distractions to fellow students" has the highest mean score of 4.28, indicating a "Very High" level of disruption. On the other hand, the behavior of item 3 "ignoring the teacher's requests to remain quiet during lectures" has the lowest mean score of 3.68, though it is still considered "High". This highlights the prevalent issue of talking inside the classroom, with varying degrees of disruption impacting the learning environment.

Table 1.2 *The Post-Test Implementation of the PSIS Intervention*

<i>Talking Inside the Classroom</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
constantly chatting with seatmate despite repeated warnings.	2.12	Low
engaging in loud conversations, disrupting the teacher's instructions.	1.96	Low
ignoring the teacher's requests to remain quiet during lectures.	1.80	Very Low
initiating off-topic discussions, derailing the focus of the class.	1.59	Very Low
persistently whispering or passing notes, causing distractions to fellow students.	1.74	Very Low
Overall Mean	1.84	Low

On the other hand, table 1.2 shows the post-test implementation of the PSIS intervention, the overall mean of disruptive behaviors related to talking inside the classroom among grade 7 students significantly decreased to 1.84, categorized as "Low". The highest mean score post-intervention is 2.12 for item 1 "constantly chatting with seatmate despite repeated warnings" indicating a "Low" level of disruption. Conversely, the lowest mean score is 1.59 for item 4 "initiating off-topic discussions, derailing the focus of the class" which falls under the "Very Low" category. This significant reduction demonstrates the effectiveness of the PSIS intervention in mitigating disruptive talking behaviors in the classroom.

The comparison of pre-test and post-test results reveals a significant improvement in the level of disruptive behaviors among grade 7 students after the PSIS intervention. Initially, the overall mean of disruptive behaviors particularly in terms of talking inside the classroom was at a high level (4.05). Following the intervention, this mean dropped dramatically to a low level (1.84). This indicates a successful reduction in behaviors such as constant chatting, loud conversations, and off-topic discussions, highlighting the effectiveness of the PSIS intervention in creating a more conducive learning environment.

Thus, the result is supported by the study of Owusu-Addo (2018) highlighted that chatting with others is a significant disruptive behavior in classrooms. This finding underscore how casual conversations among students can interrupt the flow of lessons and distract both the talkers and their classmates from the subject matter. Such disruptions can impede learning and make it challenging for teachers to maintain a focused and productive classroom environment. In connection, according to Müller (2018) the peer norms significantly influence disruptive behavior particularly talking inside the classrooms, and certain teaching practices can make this problem worse.

Level of Disruptive Behaviors Among Grade 7 Students Before and After the Utilization of PSIS Intervention in Terms of Walking Around During Lesson.

The Table 2.1 illustrates the significant difference of the level of disruptive behaviors among grade 7 students that is based in terms of walking around during lesson before the implementation of the intervention PSIS and the corresponding mean scores of every item provided.

Table 2.1 *Significant Difference of the Level of Disruptive Behaviors Among Grade 7 Students*

<i>Walking Around During Lesson</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Frequently getting up from the desk without permission, disrupting the flow of the lesson.	3.61	High
2. Aimlessly wandering around the classroom, distracting classmates.	4.14	High
3. Exhibiting restlessness by pacing back and forth, unable to stay seated.	2.39	Low
4. Ignoring the teacher's instructions to remain seated and attentive.	4.08	High
5. Continuously leaving the classroom without valid reasons, disrupting the learning environment.	4.50	Very high
Overall Mean	3.75	High

The table 2.1 present pre-test of PSIS intervention, the overall mean of disruptive behaviors related to walking around during lessons among grade 7 students was 3.75, which is categorized as "High". The behavior with the highest mean score was "continuously leaving the classroom without valid reasons, disrupting the learning environment" with a score of 4.50, indicating a "Very High" level of disruption. In contrast, the lowest mean score was 2.39 for "exhibiting restlessness by pacing back and forth, unable to stay seated" which is categorized as "Low." These behaviors collectively highlight significant disruptions in the classroom environment due to students walking around during lessons.

Table 2.2 *Overall Mean of Disruptive Behaviors Related to Walking Around During Lessons Among Grade 7 Students*

<i>Walking Around During Lesson</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Frequently getting up from the desk without permission, disrupting the flow of the lesson.	1.69	Very Low
2. Aimlessly wandering around the classroom, distracting classmates.	1.92	Low
3. Exhibiting restlessness by pacing back and forth, unable to stay seated.	1.69	Very Low
4. Ignoring the teacher's instructions to remain seated and attentive.	1.80	Very Low
5. Continuously leaving the classroom without valid reasons, disrupting the learning environment.	1.77	Very Low
Overall Mean	1.77	Very Low

After the PSIS intervention, the table 2.2 illustrate the overall mean of disruptive behaviors related to walking around during lessons among grade 7 students significantly decreased to 1.77, which is categorized as "Very Low." The highest mean score post-intervention is 1.92 for "aimlessly wandering around the classroom, distracting classmates" indicating a "Low" level of disruption. The lowest mean scores are 1.69, for both "frequently getting up from the desk without permission, disrupting the flow of the lesson" and "exhibiting restlessness by pacing back and forth, unable to stay seated" both classified as "Very Low." This substantial reduction illustrates the effectiveness of the PSIS intervention in curbing disruptive behaviors related to walking around during lessons.

The comparison of the analysis of pre-test and post-test results for disruptive behaviors related to walking around during lessons shows a marked improvement after the PSIS intervention. Before the intervention, the overall mean level of disruptive behaviors was high at 3.75, indicating frequent incidents of students getting up without permission, wandering aimlessly, and ignoring instructions. Post-intervention, this overall mean significantly decreased to 1.77, classified as very low. This suggests that the PSIS intervention was highly effective in reducing these behaviors, leading to a more stable and focused classroom environment.

This result was supported by Granero-Gallegos (2019) that high levels of disruptive behavior, especially among boys, are often tied to low intrinsic motivation and high amotivation. This means that when students aren't genuinely interested or motivated by the learning material, they're more likely to engage in disruptive behaviors like walking around the classroom during class hours. Similarly, Owusu-Addo (2018) identified common disruptions such as noise making, chatting, inattentiveness, and harassment, noting that many teachers use a teacher-centered management style. This approach can sometimes fail to engage students, further contributing to disruptive behaviors and a lack of student engagement.

Level of Disruptive Behaviors Among Grade 7 Students Before and After the Utilization of PSIS Intervention in Terms of Going Outside

The table 3.1 below shows the pre-test mean scores of the items provided pertaining to the level of the students' reading comprehension based on their vocabulary understanding as well as their prior skills before the intervention was applied.

Table 3.1 *Overall Mean of Disruptive Behaviors Related to Going Outside Among Grade 7 Students*

<i>Going outside</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Exiting the classroom without permission, disregarding the teacher's authority.	4.01	High
2. Using excuses to leave the classroom frequently, disrupting the continuity of the lesson.	3.30	Moderate
3. Demonstrating a lack of respect for classroom rules by wandering outside without authorization.	4.35	Very High
4. Creating disruptions by constantly entering and exiting the classroom.	4.10	High
5. Refusing to comply with the teacher's instructions to remain indoors, causing interruptions.	3.30	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.81	High

Before the PSIS intervention, the table 3.1 show the overall mean of disruptive behaviors related to going outside among grade 7 students was 3.81, categorized as "High." The behavior with the highest mean score was "demonstrating a lack of respect for classroom rules by wandering outside without authorization" with a score of 4.35, indicating a "Very High" level of disruption. In contrast, the lowest mean scores were 3.30 for both "using excuses to leave the classroom frequently, disrupting the continuity of the lesson" and "refusing to comply with the teacher's instructions to remain indoors, causing interruptions" both categorized as "Moderate." These behaviors underscore the significant issue of students frequently exiting the classroom without proper authorization, disrupting the learning environment.

Table 3.2 *Overall Mean of Disruptive Behaviors*

<i>Going outside</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Exiting the classroom without permission, disregarding the teacher's authority.	1.92	Low
2. Using excuses to leave the classroom frequently, disrupting the continuity of the lesson.	1.70	Very Low
3. Demonstrating a lack of respect for classroom rules by wandering outside without authorization.	2.01	Low
4. Creating disruptions by constantly entering and exiting the classroom.	2.01	Low
5. Refusing to comply with the teacher's instructions to remain indoors, causing interruptions.	1.74	Very Low
Overall Mean	1.87	Low

After the PSIS intervention, the table 3.2 illustrate the overall mean of disruptive behaviors related to going outside among grade 7 students significantly decreased to 1.87, categorized as "Low." The highest mean scores post-intervention was 2.01 for both "demonstrating a lack of respect for classroom rules by wandering outside without authorization" and "creating disruptions by constantly entering and exiting the classroom" indicating a "Low" level of disruption. The lowest mean score was 1.70 for "using

excuses to leave the classroom frequently, disrupting the continuity of the lesson," categorized as "Very Low." This reduction in disruptive behaviors highlights the positive impact of the PSIS intervention on maintaining classroom discipline regarding students going outside without permission.

Comparing the pre-test and post-test results for disruptive behaviors related to going outside shows a significant decrease following the PSIS intervention. Initially, the overall mean was high at 3.81, indicating frequent unauthorized exits and a general disregard for classroom rules. After the intervention, this mean dropped to a low level of 1.87. This demonstrates that the PSIS intervention was effective in reducing such behaviors, fostering a more disciplined and respectful classroom environment.

The result of this study is based on the study of Didaskalou (2020) which identified that a profile of high disruptive behaviors that includes a disregard for classroom rules. In line with this, Baysal (2021) stressed the critical importance of addressing these behaviors within the classroom environment. Together, these studies highlight the profound impact of disruptive behaviors, especially those that show disrespect for established classroom norms, emphasizing the urgent need for effective management strategies to foster a conducive learning atmosphere.

Level of Disruptive Behaviors Among Grade 7 Students Before and After the Utilization of PSIS Intervention in Tantrums

The pre-test result derived from Table 4.1 shows the level of disruptive behaviors among grade 7 student before the application of the PSIS intervention which also focuses in terms of tantrums for disruptive behaviors of the respondents.

Table 4.1 Overall Mean of Disruptive Behaviors Related to Tantrums Among Grade 7 Students

Tantrums	Pre-Test	Description
Displaying emotional outbursts, such as crying or screaming, in response to minor frustrations.	3.69	High
Reacting aggressively, throwing objects or slamming doors during moments of frustration.	3.19	Moderate
Resisting authority by refusing to follow instructions and engaging in disobedient behavior.	2.68	Moderate
Demonstrating disruptive behavior as a means of seeking attention or control.	3.15	Moderate
Intensifying disruptive actions when attempts are made to address or correct the behavior.	3.41	High
Overall Mean	3.22	Moderate

Before the PSIS intervention, the table 4.1 shows the overall mean of disruptive behaviors related to tantrums among grade 7 students was 3.22, categorized as "Moderate." The behavior with the highest mean score was "displaying emotional outbursts, such as crying or screaming, in response to minor frustrations" with a score of 3.69, indicating a "High" level of disruption. Conversely, the behavior with the lowest mean score was "resisting authority by refusing to follow instructions and engaging in disobedient behavior" with a score of 2.68, categorized as "Moderate." These behaviors collectively highlight the varied nature of tantrums exhibited by students, ranging from emotional outbursts to resistance of authority, impacting the classroom environment.

Table 4.2 Overall Mean of Disruptive Behaviors Related to Tantrums Among Grade 7 Students

Tantrums	Post-Test	Description
1. Displaying emotional outbursts, such as crying or screaming, in response to minor frustrations.	2.02	Low
2. Reacting aggressively, throwing objects or slamming doors during moments of frustration.	1.79	Very Low
3. Resisting authority by refusing to follow instructions and engaging in disobedient behavior.	1.66	Very Low
4. Demonstrating disruptive behavior as a means of seeking attention or control.	1.80	Very Low
5. Intensifying disruptive actions when attempts are made to address or correct the behavior.	1.66	Very Low
Overall Mean	1.79	Very Low

After the PSIS intervention, the table 4.2 portrayed the overall mean of disruptive behaviors related to tantrums among grade 7 students decreased significantly to 1.79, categorized as "Very Low." The highest mean score post-intervention was 2.02 for "displaying emotional outbursts, such as crying or screaming, in response to minor frustrations," indicating a "Low" level of disruption. The lowest mean scores were 1.66 for both "resisting authority by refusing to follow instructions and engaging in disobedient behavior" and "intensifying disruptive actions when attempts are made to address or correct the behavior," both categorized as "Very Low." This reduction demonstrates the effectiveness of the PSIS intervention in mitigating disruptive behaviors related to tantrums, fostering a more positive and conducive learning environment.

The comparison of pre-test and post-test results for disruptive behaviors related to tantrums highlights a significant improvement following the PSIS intervention. Initially, the overall mean was 3.22, indicating moderate levels of emotional outbursts, aggression, and resistance to authority. After the intervention, the overall mean dropped to 1.79, categorized as very low. This substantial reduction underscores the effectiveness of the PSIS intervention in calming emotional responses and reducing aggressive behaviors, creating a more stable and controlled classroom atmosphere.

Consequently, the result is supported by the study of Jiménez (2019) and Carlson (2022). Both corroborate the notion that emotional outbursts, such as crying or screaming, can significantly disrupt the classroom environment. These behaviors not only draw attention away from learning but also affect the emotional well-being of both the student experiencing the outburst and their classmates. Managing such emotional disruptions effectively is crucial for maintaining a supportive and focused learning environment for all students involved.

Table 5.1 Summary on the Level of Students' Disruptive Behaviors

Factors of Disruptive Behavior	Pre-Test	Descriptions	Post-Test	Descriptions
Talking Inside the Classroom	4.05	High	1.84	Low
Walking Around During Lessons	3.75	High	1.77	Very Low
Going Outside	3.81	High	1.87	Low
Tantrums	3.22	Moderate	1.79	Very Low
Overall Mean	3.70	High	1.81	Low

Correspondingly, the PSIS intervention was highly effective in reducing disruptive behaviors among grade 7 students across all measured indicators. Before the intervention, disruptive behaviors related to talking inside the classroom had an overall mean score of 4.05, categorized as "High," which dropped significantly to 1.84, categorized as "Low," post-intervention. Similarly, behaviors related to walking around during lessons saw a decrease from an overall mean of 3.75 ("High") to 1.77 ("Very Low"). For behaviors related to going outside, the overall mean decreased from 3.81 ("High") to 1.87 ("Low"). Lastly, disruptive behaviors associated with tantrums showed a reduction from a moderate level with an overall mean of 3.22 to a very low level with a mean of 1.79. This comprehensive reduction across all categories highlights the intervention's effectiveness in fostering a more disciplined and conducive learning environment. Overall, the mean score 3.70 which obtained from pre-test ranges to the description "High" to the mean score 1.81 obtained from post-test which is described as Low. This indicates that the disruptive behavior of the students have lessen after the implementation of the intervention created.

Significant Difference Between Pre-Test and Post-Test Employing the PROJECT Proximity Control, Signal Interference, Ignoring Students, and Students' Arrangement (PSIS) Intervention

Table 6 illustrates the significant difference of the pre-test and post-test of the intervention upon the implementation of PSIS to the Grade 7 students which serves as the respondents of this study.

Table 6. Significant Difference Between Pre-Test and Post-Test

Type of Test	N	df	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Decision $\alpha = 0.05$
Pretest	89		3.70	0.680	28.536	< .001	Significant
Post-Test	89	88	1.81	0.170			

The overall result illustrates that the level of the disruptive behavior of the Grade 7 students during the pre-test having a total mean of 3.70 which is described as High and obtained a standard deviation of 0.680. On the other hand, from the post-test, it accumulates a total mean of 1.81 which is described as Low and obtained a standard deviation of 0.170.

Moreover, based on the result of the significant difference of the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents from Grade 7 which undergone the intervention, the T-value of -28.536 and p-value of <.001 indicates that the null hypothesis of this study will be rejected, since the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the intervention is found effective since and result illustrates that the actions taken is significant and implies that the hypothesis will be rejected.

Insights Can You Share to the School Administrators, Teachers, and Stakeholders with Regards to Action Intervention Taken

The major themes and sample statements for research question number 3 were presented in Table 6. Participants had their responses to their own experiences. From the answers of the participants, there are three major themes have emerged: (1) Understanding the Causes of Disruptive Behavior; (2) Impact on Academic Performance; and (3) Effective Intervention Strategies.

Table 7. Themes and Sample Statements on The Insights They Share to the School Administrators, Teachers, and Stakeholders with Regards to the Action/Intervention Taken

Emerging Themes	Sample Statements
Understanding the Causes of Disruptive Behavior	✓ "The students who did not behave can cause interruptions while we, the teachers are discussing." (FGD-03)
	✓ "There are times when the teacher has an attitude or we do not like her because she is boring when teaching. That is why some of my classmates go outside while she is discussing the lesson." (IDI-02)
	✓ "For me, my father is always shouting. Even for a small mistake I make, he yells and shouts. Maybe because of this, when I am inside the classroom, I want to distract my classmates". (IDI-04)
	✓ "A structured and engaging classroom can reduce disruptive behaviors. We need to adapt our teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of our students." (FGD-06)
Impact on Academic Performance	✓ "When I spend too much usage on my phone or playing video games during classes hours, I end up doing poorly on my tasks and tests and ends up confiscating the phone." (IDI-01)
	✓ "When I get along with my classmates, I feel more motivated to do well in school. But if I'm having problems with friends, my grades suffer." (IDI-03)
	✓ "Talking and walking during the lesson, as disruptive behaviors of the students, affect their learning." (FGD-04)

Effective Intervention Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ "There are times when students cannot engage quickly with the lesson, and the set activities are delayed for a few minutes, resulting in the class not being completed." (FGD-01) ✓ "The behavioral support program they have conducted at my school has helped me control my outbursts and focus more on my studies." (IDI-05) ✓ "I try harder in school because my teachers recognize and reward my efforts. It feels good to be acknowledged." (IDI-04) ✓ "When the PSIS was implemented, there was a big improvement in the behavior of grade 7 students." (FGD-02) ✓ "The Project PSIS and trainings in DepEd really help to develop my strategies that I can apply in my classroom for addressing the common disruptive behaviors of my students." (FGD-05)
-----------------------------------	---

Personal challenges significantly contribute to disruptive behaviors in the classroom, as students often find it difficult to manage the emotional and psychological stress from their home environments. For example, a student dealing with family conflicts, poverty, or the loss of a loved one may act out, defy rules, or become easily distracted. These behaviors are often expressions of the student's emotional turmoil and their struggle to process these feelings healthily. Teacher attitudes greatly influence student behavior. Supportive, patient, and understanding teachers foster a positive classroom atmosphere that promotes good behavior. Empathetic and non-judgmental teachers help students feel comfortable and valued, leading to increased cooperation and less misbehavior. In contrast, authoritarian, critical, or dismissive teachers can create a negative environment, causing students to feel anxious, defensive, or disengaged, which can increase misbehavior.

Disruptive behaviors in the classroom significantly impact academic performance, affecting not only the student involved but also their classmates. Such behaviors lower the academic achievement of the disruptive student and reduce the engagement and motivation of others, compromising the overall learning environment. This can lead to decreased grades, lower academic achievement, and even higher dropout rates. The Responsive Approach, utilizing Project PSIS (Proximity control, Signal interference, Ignoring, and Student arrangement), is an effective strategy to minimize disruptive behaviors in grade 7 students. Proximity control involves teachers moving around the room to engage with students, reducing off-task behavior. Signal interference uses nonverbal cues to signal disapproval, while ignoring minor disruptions allows students to self-correct. Strategic student arrangement also helps manage classroom dynamics. By combining these techniques, teachers can create a structured yet responsive environment that enhances student engagement and minimizes disruptions, improving the overall learning experience.

One of the insights of the students in disruptive behavior was difficult personal circumstances. Students facing difficult personal circumstances, such as learning disabilities or ADHD, may exhibit disruptive behavior. Educators should be aware of these issues and provide necessary support. Therefore, educators must strive to create inclusive classrooms where all students feel valued, respected, and supported. This involves implementing differentiated instruction, leveraging assistive technologies, and fostering a culture of empathy and understanding (McGarr, 2021). Teaching time and engagement are significantly impacted by disruptive behaviors among students, leading to a decrease in the quality of teaching and learning. Disruptive behaviors in the classroom can result in less classroom engagement time, which negatively impacts students' academic achievements. Teachers report that constant interruptions to deal with off-task behavior make it difficult for them to teach effectively, leading to incomplete lessons and decreased student engagement (Franklin & Harrington, 2019). On the other hand, the study of Escandallo and Baradillo (2024) explained that when students were taught with various strategies during the teaching and learning process, they will establish focus and be able to learn effectively.

Conclusion

After a comprehensive analysis of the data collected during this research study, the researchers were able to draw several key conclusions that directly address the research questions and objectives.

1. The research results indicate that the implementation of the Project PSIS intervention had a significant impact on reducing disruptive behaviors among grade 7 students. Before the intervention, the students exhibited high levels of disruptive behaviors such as talking in class (mean of 4.05), walking around during lessons (mean of 3.75), going outside (mean of 3.81), and tantrums (mean of 3.22). However, after the intervention, these disruptive behaviors decreased substantially, with the mean scores dropping to 1.84 (low), 1.77 (very low), 1.87 (low), and 1.79 (very low), respectively. These findings suggest that the Project PSIS intervention was effective in squashing disruptive behaviors in the classroom.

2. The study found a significant relationship between disruptive behaviors and the Project PSIS (Proximity control, Signal interference, Ignoring, and Student arrangement), underscoring its effectiveness as a classroom management strategy. Project PSIS is designed to help educators mitigate disruptive behaviors among grade 7 students through a multifaceted approach. Proximity control involves teachers strategically positioning themselves near students who are prone to disruptions, thereby curbing negative behaviors through their presence. Signal interference uses non-verbal cues to subtly redirect students' attention without interrupting the flow of the lesson. Ignoring minor disruptions strategically avoids reinforcing attention-seeking behaviors, while student arrangement optimizes seating plans to minimize conflicts and distractions. Together, these techniques create a structured and supportive classroom environment that reduces the incidence of disruptive behaviors, promoting a more conducive learning atmosphere. By implementing Project PSIS, educators can effectively manage their classrooms, ensuring that all students have the opportunity to engage in and benefit from the

educational process.

3. In the study, the quantitative findings were reinforced by key themes identified through thematic analysis of the qualitative data. Overall, the results validated the quantitative component of the research, reflecting the participants' and informants' responses during the interviews. The alignment between the quantitative and qualitative findings underscores the robustness of the study's conclusions.

4. During the integration of data from both the quantitative and qualitative phases, it was evident that the findings were interconnected, demonstrating a cohesive relationship between the two sets of results. The qualitative data enriched the quantitative results by providing a deeper understanding of the levels of disruptive behaviors observed before and after the Project PSIS intervention. Specifically, the themes that emerged from the qualitative analysis not only supported the quantitative findings but also offered a nuanced explanation of the changes in disruptive behavior levels. This integration highlighted the complexity and profoundness of the behaviors, showing how the intervention impacted them in various dimensions. Consequently, the combined insights from both phases provided a comprehensive view of the effectiveness of the Project PSIS intervention, offering both statistical validation and contextual depth.

Therefore, the recommendations for addressing the disruptive behaviors of grade 7 students include the implementation of the Project PSIS (Proximity Control, Signal Interference, Ignoring, and Student Arrangement) and specialized training programs offered by the Department of Education. These strategies are essential for creating a classroom environment where students can engage and interact without causing disturbances. The consistent application of these recommendations is crucial to ensure that all students can participate in a productive and harmonious learning atmosphere.

For these recommendations to be effective, it is necessary for educators to apply them consistently with the support of parents, school administrators, stakeholders, and the broader school community. Collaborative efforts among all parties involved will help establish a conducive teaching and learning environment. By working together, they can create a structured and supportive setting that minimizes disruptive behaviors, allowing for more effective instruction and improved student outcomes.

References

- Boyce, C and Palena, N. (2006). *Conducting In-Depth Interviews: A Guide for Designing and Conducting In-Depth Interviews for Evaluation Input*.
- Burden, P. R. (2020). *Classroom management: Creating a successful K-12 learning community*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Caldarella et al., (2021). "Stop doing that!": Effects of teacher reprimands on student disruptive behavior and engagement. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, 23(3), 163-173. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1098300720935101>
- Carlson, G. A., Singh, M. K., Amaya-Jackson, L., Benton, T. D., Althoff, R. R., Bellonci, C., ... & McClellan, J. M. (2023). Narrative review: impairing emotional outbursts: what they are and what we should do about them. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 62(2), 135-150.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage
- Denzin, N and Lincoln, Y. (2003). *Turning Points in Qualitative Research*.
- Didaskalou, E., Briesch, A. M., Volpe, R. J., & Roussi-Vergou, C. (2020). Psychometric properties of the classroom observation of engagement, disruptive, and disrespectful behavior (COEDD) in Greek school children. *International Journal of School & Educational Psychology*, 10(3), 303-315
- Escandallo, J.C., & Baradillo, D. (2024). A sequential explanatory approach on the relationship between social literacy and student engagement as mediated by English speaking skills. *EPR International of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*.
- Franklin, H., & Harrington, I. (2019). A review into effective classroom management and strategies for student engagement: Teacher and student roles in today's classrooms. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*.
- Ganaban, J. (2023). Behavior Management Approaches Employed by Teachers for Diverse Learners in Junior and Senior High School. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 7(4), 299-304. <https://10.5281/zenodo.7683011>
- Granero-Gallegos, A., Gómez-López, M., Baena-Extremera, A., & Martínez-Molina, M. (2020). Interaction effects of disruptive behaviour and motivation profiles with teacher competence and school satisfaction in secondary school physical education. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(1), 114.
- Herman, K. C., Reinke, W. M., Dong, N., & Bradshaw, C. P. (2022). Can effective classroom behavior management increase student achievement in middle school? Findings from a group randomized trial. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 114(1), 144.
- Holmes, C., Briant, A., Kahn, R., Deater-Deckard, K., & Kim-Spoon, J. (2019). Structural home environment effects on developmental trajectories of self-control and adolescent risk taking. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 48, 43-55.

- Jangmo, A., Stålhandske, A., Chang, Z., Chen, Q., Almqvist, C., Feldman, I., ... & Larsson, H. (2019). Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, school performance, and effect of medication. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 58(4), 423-432.
- Kim, S., Crooks, C. V., Bax, K., & Shokoohi, M. (2021). Impact of trauma-informed training and mindfulness-based social-emotional learning program on teacher attitudes and burnout: A mixed-methods study. *School mental health*, 13(1), 55-68.
- Leonard, S., Haruna, M. S., Inikpi, O. H., & Ojochenemi, U. B. (2023). Strategies for Managing Disruptive Behaviours Among Public Secondary School Students in Classrooms in Kogi East Education Zone Nigeria. *Strategies*, 1(2).
- Mack, N., Woodsong, C., MacQueen, K. M., & Guest, G. (2005). Qualitative research research methods. *Family Health International*. 6(1), 455-461. doi: 10.11591/ijere. v9i3.20614
- McGarr, O. (2021). The use of virtual simulations in teacher education to develop pre-service teachers' behaviour and classroom management skills: implications for reflective practice. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 47(2), 274-286.
- McGrath, K. F., & Van Bergen, P. (2019). Attributions and emotional competence: why some teachers experience close relationships with disruptive students (and others don't). *Teachers and Teaching*, 25(3), 334-357.
- Moreira, V., & Del Consuelo, N. (2019). Programa de intervención para disminuir conductas disruptivas de un grupo de estudiantes de la escuela Río Coca de Guayaquil, 2019.
- Müller, C. M., Hofmann, V., Begert, T., & Cillessen, A. H. (2018). Peer influence on disruptive classroom behavior depends on teachers' instructional practice. *Journal of applied developmental psychology*, 56, 99-108.
- Nanyele, S., Kuranchie, A., & Owusu-Addo, A. (2018). Classroom management practices and student disruptive behavior. *Integrity Journal of Education and Training*, 2(2), 6-14.
- Olivier, E., Galand, B., Hospel, V., & Dellisse, S. (2020). Understanding behavioural engagement and achievement: The roles of teaching practices and student sense of competence and task value. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 90(4), 887-909.
- Post, P. B., Grybush, A. L., Flowers, C., & Elmadani, A. (2020). Impact of child-teacher relationship training on teacher attitudes and classroom behaviors. *International Journal of Play Therapy*, 29(3), 119.
- Ruslin, R., Mashuri, S., Rasak, M. S. A., Alhabsyi, F., & Syam, H. (2022). Semi-structured Interview: A methodological reflection on the development of a qualitative research instrument in educational studies. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, 12(1), 22-29.
- Sailor, W., Skrtic, T. M., Cohn, M., & Olmstead, C. (2021). Preparing teacher educators for statewide scale-up of multi-tiered system of support (MTSS). *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 44(1), 24-41.
- Scholtz, S. E. (2021). Sacrifice is a step beyond convenience: A review of convenience sampling in psychological research in Africa. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 47(1), 1-12.
- Skinner, C. (2020). Quantitative research. In *Handbook for research students in the social sciences* (pp. 215-224). Routledge.
- Smith, T. E., Sheridan, S. M., Kim, E. M., Park, S., & Beretvas, S. N. (2020). The effects of family-school partnership interventions on academic and social-emotional functioning: A meta-analysis exploring what works for whom. *Educational Psychology Review*, 32, 511-544.
- Umar, U., & Khair, R. (2022). Teacher'S Strategies In Reducing Students' Disruptive Behavior In Indonesian Efl Classroom. *English Review: Journal of English Education*, 10(2), 543-554.
- Walker, S., & Graham, L. (2021). At risk students and teacher-student relationships: student characteristics, attitudes to school and classroom climate. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 25(8), 896-913.
- Wangdi, T., & Namgyel, S. (2022). Classroom to reduce student disruptive behavior: action research. *Mextesol Journal*, 46(1), 1-11. https://www.mextesol.net/journal/index.php?page=journal&id_article=46323
- Xiong, Y., Qin, X., Wang, Q., & Ren, P. (2021). Parental involvement in adolescents' learning and academic achievement: Cross-lagged effect and mediation of academic engagement. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 50(9), 1811-1823.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jonelson C. Escandallo

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Novie May C. Manliguez

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Kheyzza M. Panizales

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Venus M. Pupa

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Alaiza Mae C. Villamor

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Deveyvon L. Espinosa

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Conie B. Cerna

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Kristy Jane R. Muegna

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Regine L. Generalao

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines